

Post-minimal-contextualism-critical-modernism Reality

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RESUMEN

En el documento se trata de evaluar la arquitectura de hoy como parte de un 'star system', donde la originalidad es el objetivo principal del objeto arquitectónico. Tras esto, se intenta crear una teoría basada en la pérdida de parte de la individualidad del arquitecto con el fin de lograr un mejor resultado basado en la coherencia de todo el sistema construido: una ciudad, un pueblo, una calle, etc. El reconocimiento de los signos de un lugar es parte de ese proceso, no con la intención de copiar la realidad circundante, pero con el diseño de interpretar sus principales características. El proceso depurativo resultante borrará los signos de que ya han perdido su significado y no contribuyen para la identificación de la arquitectura de un sitio, hacia un reconocimiento que se desarrolla a partir de la observación a gran escala del paisaje hacia los detalles en la arquitectura. La coherencia es por lo tanto el propósito principal del proceso, si se trata de aplicar a un contexto histórico, un asentamiento urbano popular o un barrio moderno.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Coherencia, Arquitectura Popular, Señal, Forma, Realismo*

ABSTRACT

The paper tries to evaluate today's architecture as part of a 'star system' where originality is the main purpose of the architectural object. Upon this it is tried to create a theory based in the loss of part of the individuality of the architect in order to achieve a greater result based upon the coherence of a whole built system: a city, a village, a street, etc. The recognition of a place's Signs is part of that process, not with the intent of copying the surrounding reality, but to interpret its main features. The resulting depurative process will obliterate those Signs that already have lost their meaning and do not contribute to the recognition of a site's architecture, to an appreciation that evolves from the large scale observation of the landscape to the detail in architecture. Coherence is therefore the main purpose of the process, whether it's applied to a historical context, a popular urban settlement or a contemporary neighbourhood.

KEYWORDS: *Coherence, Popular Architecture, Sign, Shape, Realism*

Fig. 1. 'The Alibi'. Source: author's drawing, 2012.

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INTRODUCION

The need to take a new approach to the term Realism is closely connected to Architecture as it is practiced today. The overload of information carried on by the mass media led to the establishment of a type of communication that needs to stand out to be recognizable among the excess of words and images that surrounds us.

The need to overlap all the information that competes to get our attention is therefore the cause of the birth of an architectural star system that can only communicate through bright images of uncanny originality. As if the road signs over bland buildings aligned along the highways in Las Vegas that Venturi and Scott Brown¹ mentioned since 1966 have become THE architecture: intense and vibrant neon buildings trying to claim our attention.

Fig. 2. Las-Vegas-strip,-1966-©-Venturi,-Scott-Brown-and-Associates,-Inc.-,-Philadelphia. Source: <http://andreasangelidakis.blogspot.com/2012/01/postcards-from-edge.html>, [2012]

The building as an exception to the rule mustn't be mistaken with the need to create urban references, for instance. In a city, usually composed of a rule that is a constant image created by its main features (housing, for instance), the church, the tower, the square are those exceptions that give us references, but if the Agbar tower works among the 'ruling system', it would be, perhaps, just another building in Las Vegas.

Therefore the use of the exception to the rule, in Architectural means, must be a careful choice, according to their surroundings. Eduardo Souto Moura mentioned once in a classⁱⁱ that the large white building, design by Siza Vieira, were both have their offices, acted as a useful counterpoint to the surrounding urban context. However, the impossibility to control the development of those same surroundings led to the construction of high rise buildings that annulled Siza's building and the original pre-existing urban structure.

Fig. 3. Álvaro Siza and Eduardo Souto Moura's office building, in the picture's background. Source: author's pictures, 2012

THE VINDICATION OF BANALITY

The necessity of originality or individualism at all costs was, however, a process that begun way before the event of television (the cause of all evils...). Adolf Loosⁱⁱⁱ criticized the excess of decorative elements or sign over carried by traditional architecture, and proposed simplicity as a result of the wining of technique over aesthetics. As for the Modernism, they also intended to uniform architecture in general through the use of a codified architecture that would abolish cultural boundaries.

However, the pursuit of a rule, a constant image, contributed to the above mentioned situation where the exceptional is... rule. In arts in general (where architecture can still find its place) the past century marked the abandonment of what we may call the 'defining elements of art', or the essential features upon which we can recognize, interpret and evaluate art.

The Sign (or the 'Thing')^{iv} was the first to disappear as shapes became abstract and strange to our visual recognition. However their Significant ('Name') remained, as Marie-Thérèse lingered in Picasso's paintings, and the Villa Savoye was still a house. Finally we were left with only the Significance (or 'Concept'), where someone was 'hidden' in a white canvas or tried to promenade in an open gallery.

Fig. 4. Marie-Thérèse Walter, picture (date unknown) and painting ('Le Rêve', 1932). Source: <http://webartacademy.com/the-women-of-pablo-picasso-marie-therese-walter-and-picasso>, [03.2012]

Therefore we had to rely only in the artist's word to recognize Sign, Significant and Significance in his masterpiece, hanging on a wall or placed in a plot. A visual and liveable art became in this process solely an oral art: 'in Artist we trust'.

An heritage left to us by Minimalism, an architectural movement as valid as any other, was therefore the possibility to design abstract shapes and base on a theoretical discourse the motivations and meanings upon 'that' project belongs 'there'.

Therefore we reach today's single 'defining element of art' that is ethics: if we must trust in an oral explication to justify a shape, we must only rely upon the artist's deontological code to be sure that a 'trendy' image wasn't the main intention of one's proposal.

Even if Kenneth Frampton^v defends that the last generation of modernists have found in the 'genius loci' the necessary elements to interpret and respond to their 'object's'^{vi} surroundings (the 'critical regionalism'), therefore recovering the lost 'defining elements of art', the truth is that in some cases those elements are still hidden for the more common observer.

Fig. 5. Kosuth, Joseph. 'One and Three Chairs'. 1965. Source: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/One_and_Three_Chairs, [03.2012]

COHERENCE

It is therefore exposed the necessity of using signs in architecture in order to make it understandable for a cultural and a non-cultural audience. As we no longer believe in a universal modern architecture emptied of any cultural references, the use of the above mentioned singularity in architecture models is also a non-response to a type of architecture that has the intention of building our landscape in a larger scale.

That leads us, of course, to the notion of using Reality as a cultural background for our present and future proposals. This stance, which we can call 'Realism' or, at least, inside trends closer to 'Realism' it's not supported, for example, in a strong political basis as it was the Italian neo-realism^{vii}, not even in a practical purpose of using local materials and techniques (as an evolution of the construction processes we have, probably, achieved an equilibrium where large scale prefabrication is used in small elements than can be produced locally).

Which are therefore the main features of 'this' Realism needed in today's architecture? The use of Sign, Significant and Significance can only induce to one method: a more empirical interpretation of the context, with a more obvious reading of its features. And, as a result, rather than Realism we obtain Coherence, which is born when the 'object' can insert himself 'peacefully' in the surrounding environment.

A 'Realistic Coherence' implies therefore the notion of 'boundaries'^{viii}, more intellectual and imagistic than physical, among which the features to be used in a proposal must be searched. The area defined by these boundaries has no specific size or extension, since it is defined by the elements that allow us to identify the 'genius loci' (a notion also redefined in a more practical – physical? – way). The 'Realistic Coherence' is contained among the limits of a region, a town, a neighbourhood or even a street where the observer recognizes its signs.

Fig. 6. Oporto city nearby the Douro river. Source: <http://portugalepopeiajoaodamestra.blogspot.com/>, [03.2012]

ARCHITECTURE(S), OBSERVER(S), USER(S)

The notion that architecture has an observer (also a user) leads us to a dialectic system where architecture strides: the competing Popular and Erudite context, that we often forget, but still exists.

As architects, we mustn't be presumptuous to a point where the only possible debate in this discipline is our 'own' production. And also we must keep in mind that 'Popular' is not a synonym of old, unsound and ruined buildings remembered in Popular Architecture compendiums.

This is a very important question, at the least in the Portuguese context upon which the present paper was elaborated. Architecture by architects consists in a small percentage of the built landscape, as other technicians are able to design 'architecture'. As so, our contemporary architectural scenery, specially the one composed by single family houses (linked or not to suburban sites) is mainly composed by a 'superficially sketched' model, often based in a common Type of the surrounding built environment, upon which the dweller applies its own (real or intended) references.

This is consequently the definition of Popular Architecture: types and models by non-architects where an outside culture's signs, erudite or not, are applied. This system of architecture exposes the existence of a determined boundary upon which the Popular Type is contained, but at the same time shows that that limit is crossed, as the influences from different cultures arouse in the built Models.

Therefore, in this definition there is no timeline or specific date upon which 'Popular' 'lives', meaning that nowadays it is still possible to have contact with popular cultures, architectural or not.

So, the main difference with Vernacular Architecture is that this Type is born solely inside a well defined cultural group without outside interferences. Here it is easier to define a precise limit, but the exchange of knowledge has been a process that begun long ago and crossed many boundaries. Therefore, an isolate Type with no outside features is more and more difficult to find in any given culture (eastern or not), if not impossible. To

say this is to realise that pure vernacular architecture is almost impossible to find nowadays, while Popular Architecture is still alive.

Fig. 7. The Vernacular house nearby Leiria, Portugal, in the 1960's, whose examples are today very scarce.
Source: author's drawing upon photographs taken at the time (2010)

But the references that make architecture Popular are, most of the times, an idealistic image of a supposed ancient popular architecture, based upon classical signs, misunderstood as 'typical of the Portuguese popular architecture', juxtaposed to very obvious and direct 'traditional' elements with no actual meaning or purpose.

REALITY(IES)

Therefore we can identify two opposite postures, according to the source of the 'architecture':

a) One, the 'architect's architecture', where the 'genius loci' seizes to evoke the site's main features, physical and psychological. If using as a reference popular architecture, the used criteria is based upon the scale, shape or 'presence' of the model, but in a 'purified' way. An example is Siza's Malagueira district, a high density low scale housing project, based upon patio-houses whose typology can evolve: the same house can begun as a one bedroom and grow to a five bedroom dwelling. However, and despite the pure, white monolithic shapes of the project, the architect, in an class^{ix}, said that the projection of one's personality on the house (like painting ochre stripes around the windows – common in local popular architecture) didn't depreciate the project's intentions.

Fig. 8. Malagueira neighborhood, Évora, Portugal. The first picture shows white only buildings, while the second shows how dwellers added some popular signs like the ocher stripes. Source: [09.2009], <http://www.flickr.com/photos/ekain/2795269911/>; [09.2009], [http://www.flickr.com/photos/10234308@N05/2795270715>](http://www.flickr.com/photos/10234308@N05/2795270715/)

b) Two, the 'common man's architecture' in whose houses are projected idealistic lifestyles brought from a near past. This 'short term memory' induces the use, as it was said, of signs of an erudite architecture evoking higher living standards, and are commonly elements that although keeping their Sign and Significant, have no longer Significance or its past use: stone columns that no longer support anything, as well as for other stonework (around the windows) that no longer support the window's aperture. More significantly, these elements are juxtaposed to traditional housing model born in the common type house inside a determined boundary.

It is curious to observe that, as an architectural movement, popular architecture is also influenced by particular fashions or moments in history where the contemporary or the traditional are valorised (or their respective interpretations): sometimes modernist elements are juxtaposed to the popular model, while in other moments the ochre stripes or Doric columns are preferred.

Fig. 9. Contemporary popular houses nearby Alcobaça, Portugal. The stonework around the windows, the columns, all signs of a supposed past which never existed in the region. Source: author's photos (2000).

CONTEXTUALISE

There is a motive why these different contexts must be explored thoroughly since, as architects, our place of intervention is composed by all kinds of contexts and surroundings. In those are included well preserved heritage domains, mischaracterized urban fabrics, scattered built rural landscapes and so on.

The notion of making use of a 'Realistic Coherence' is therefore linked to the necessity to respect or 'heal' the 'genius loci'. However, an architect, involved in a serious practise of architecture (opposed to those who uncritically design all-purpose models), doesn't deny its own epoch, its own status of a being inserted in a contemporary erudite cultural movement.

Fig. 10. Prince Perfeito Avenue, Gulpilhares, Portugal. Although all houses were designed by architects, it's hard to talk about coherence once they are all contiguous. Source: author's photos (2012).

Nevertheless, as we have seen at the beginning of this article, contemporary architecture is much attached to the notion of individuality, where the cult of an artist's and an object's

uniqueness is chased. In this scenario, do we have any guarantee that it is possible to make the architectural object part of a whole, besides the architect's own watermark?

Hardly, since uniqueness is praised, therefore the object will stand out (or intend to) from any given surroundings: erudite, popular, contemporary or heritage sites. And so, the main feature of the Realism defended in this paper, Coherence, it's not obtained, since the landscape is made entirely of individual entities, and not a continuous system.

The same can be said of a Popular environment, where different 'fashions' have resulted in different models over the years, but, as in the example above, that doesn't legitimize a posture where singularity is the only feature to be pursued. And that can be applied to an architect who is going to make an erudite proposal on a popular environment.

Fig. 10. António Sérgio Street, Gulpilhares, Portugal. The Popular houses use different aesthetic solutions, compromising coherence, but the more disturbing element remains the 'contemporary' house in the right, although it's quality is doubtful. Source: author's photos (2012).

LEGISLATE

Urban planning these days is far more careful than in the decades before us: the recognition of a contained area with determined features that worth keeping lead authorities to create, as we know, a whole set of rules capable of preventing the misrepresentation of a site with a strong heritage legacy. But also, when designing upon a white sheet (in other words, legislating future deployments) the same posture is applied and laws are created in order to prevent the distortion of the future urban fabric.

There are a few questions that can be aroused upon this. The first one is to determine where is the limit that defines heritage preservation and a limitation to the architect's work. The same can be used in the legislation applied to future urbanizations, with the same implications. In the first case we are preserving our past, in the second one, we are protecting our future.

These seem to be very clear backgrounds with very clear purposes. But the main question that we ask ourselves is what to do about the grey areas where there is no clear historic background, and the future as already begun? For example, the contemporary popular architecture areas that define our territory, but commonly considered worthless.

OUR PRESENT IS OUR FUTURE PAST

Common sense tells us that to obliterate all kinds of urban settlements and buildings that don't correspond to our criteria of quality is impossible. Common sense also tells us that obtaining consensus about those criteria is also unfeasible. But the fact is that most buildings are here to stay, meaning that in a near or far future, those buildings will consist on part of our inherited architecture.

A book, very important to Portuguese architecture legacy, was made in the early 1960's to collect examples of 'Popular Architecture in Portugal'^x. Many models were collected,

Types were defined according to different regions, including my own hometown (the outskirts of Alcobaça, Portugal). Through an empirical observation of the landscape I could see that the Models present in that book had already disappeared, and the Models (and Types) that composed our popular heritage were others. A visit to the city hall confirmed what I suspected: our 'new heritage' where the buildings being built in the early sixties, along with more recent types, nowadays more common, that, according to the same logic, will consist in our 'future past'.

Fig. 11. Popular from the 1960's, Alcobaça, Portugal. Symmetry and other signs are used upon the same model, which was being built at the same time that 'Popular Architecture in Portugal' was being made, based upon 'that time's past'. Source: author's drawings upon Alcobaça's City Hall licensing processes.

Therefore, despite our personal evaluation of this or that Type with endowed quality, we must realize that our present popular Types, juxtaposed with the most diverse signs (rustic stonework, classical columns or exuberant colours) are possibly also our future past. Therefore the purpose of the architect is not to contribute with another dissonant model, but to try to participate in the making of a whole coherent system.

Fig. 12. Popular from the 1960's, Alcobaça, Portugal, nowadays'. Source: author's photos (2000).

THE PURIFYING PROCESS

The process that will lead to such a procedure is, in the first place, to forget about the architectural 'star system' where architecture is only valid if it stands out. Second, we must compromise ourselves to produce a serious typological study in order to determine a site's Type, that can only be obtained if we 'undress' Models of its decorative elements (meaning, the dissonant signs). Finally, the purifying process will reveal the true reference capable of guiding us through the conceptual process.

In the above arguments, we talked about empirical observation of our surroundings. However, empiricism is a notion that is completely different from superficiality or immediacy^{xi}. So, it does not imply the signs that are the first to arouse once the model is seen: it's not Naive Realism^{xii}.

In the above mentioned case-study, the surroundings of Alcobaça, the city hall revealed a popular house of the 1960's composed by a single small building, with a two-sloped roof in tile, whose main façade was a symmetrical system with a central door and two side

windows. Through this feature we can recognize an erudite heritage (symmetry), but the house's main feature was that this element consisted in the first one of a larger system that added volume after volume to the first one, according to the dweller's needs. Those could be more living space or practical areas for livestock or workshops.

Fig. 13. Popular from the 1960's, Alcobaça, Portugal, where we can observe how the house grew through volumes that were more practical and less 'noble': poorer materials, lower volumes, etc. Source: author's photos and drawings (2000).

Therefore, at the end of the process the 'house' was an 'organism' composed by several volumes. An empirical appreciation of the whole fabric reveals, from the street level, this fact, but it's even more obvious when seen from above and far. Here stands the fundamental difference with the 'primary home' idea, based in a long term memory instance, where a single depurated volume was considered.

This is a method that can define a process implied in the 'Realistic Coherence', which consists in a type of approach that evolves from a larger scale to the detailing range. So, to remain coherent in this background is to search for the scale of the interventions, the composed modules and the rule that dominates a street, a road or a village in its extent. And it is to exclude 'smaller' signs like stripes, window shapes, columns or tiled roofs. Legislation is an important feature in this matter since it may oblige the use of a determined strong sign can possibly induce to the obliteration of others in order to affirm our own Contemporary status: to be coherent is never to produce a 'pastiche'.

Fig. 14. House in Taveiro (2007-2009), Alcobaça, Portugal. The project was based in the Type of house still common in the surrounding area, where a primary volume (rectangular plan, double sloped roof) is complemented with additional volumes. When seen from above, the idea was to blend the different volumes among the houses nearby (google earth image above left) but also to express its contemporary roots through detail, observed at close. Source: author's project, photos and drawings (2009).

CONCLUDING

The above mentioned examples are just some of the situations where the 'large scale to detail' architecture appreciation and production can be applied. Here, History has a large part of the intervention method since it is referred a popular background built through time in a rural/urban context. That is not always the case, since our cities also have a historical background, for instance.

But, even when 'history is being made', we must take into account that, if we are not creating the rule, we must be coherent to what is already made. And nowadays, despite the fact of a neighbourhood of houses is entirely designed by architects, if each one applies their own 'vision', the result will also be a sum of autistic elements.

Coherence is therefore a main feature to be respected, based in a 'short term memory' (what we see and can still remember) that make each piece of architecture part of a whole.

Fig. 15. Drawings of the still existing models of Popular Architecture from the 1960's in the surroundings of Alcobaça, Portugal, who served as a beginning of an investigation which the present paper is one of the examples. Source: author's drawings

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